

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY INITIATIVES TOWARDS RURAL INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT: AN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

AYUSH KUMAR*; KAVITA SINGH**

*ASSISTANT PROFESSOR
IMS, MAHATMA GANDHI KASHI VIDYAPITH, VARANASI
(A U.P. STATE UNIVERSITY)

**MBA, UPTU, LUCKNOW.

ABSTRACT

Social Responsibility is the commitment of corporate houses towards the society. Corporations must take into account, their decision and operations that are going to affect the masses at large. CSR shows the way business achieves ethical and moral standards and gets an equitable distribution of economic, social and natural resources to fulfill the suppositions of their stakeholders. Corporate Social Responsibility is not only confined towards customers but also towards their employees, suppliers, investors/shareholders and government too as they actually constitute a society surrounded with an interactive environment. This research is mainly focus on holistic view of CSR and recent CSR practices of corporate houses to develop the rural areas through providing basic infrastructural services and also trying to remove regional imbalance caused due to operational loopholes or inability of authorized agencies.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, Sustainable Development, Holistic Rural Development, Infrastructural Services.

INTRODUCTION

Past decades have accounted increasing importance of corporate social responsibility, especially as concern about social upliftment and initiation of various public welfare programs. These efforts support the government in social making and human growth that further contributes to national development. It is very pure concept that there is strong relation between business, society and environment. Business utilizes the resources of environment and society, to serve the peoples and make the profit in return. But it is not only the money matter that business deals with, they must have to protect that resources and make the market more inclusive and sustainable for the long term revival of the business. They have to make the peoples able and a healthy environment for businesses, so that they can participate in various economic activities and improve their standard of living. CSR is a tool or obligation, under which the corporate houses perform their moral, ethical and legal responsibilities for the development of the society through various way. In the era of globalization various social problems become hurdle in the development of the country such as migration, employment, climate change, income inequalities, social disintegration, peace, crime, environmental risk and hazards. The business, who exploited the resources of the society, is equally responsible to solve these social problems. The Henry Ford, founder of Ford Motors Company has mentioned business in very exact words

in terms of its responsibility towards society as “A business that makes nothing but money is a poor business.” While CSR activities done by business organizations is an important step for the society, it is equally important for the development of rural areas of country like India, where resources are very limited for the growth prospects and diversity too make the path of sustainable and inclusive development more challenging. The dialogue session of World Business Council for Sustainable Development announced a good but debatable relational between CSR and Sustainable Development, as CSR is integral part of Sustainable Development (WBCSD, 2000)

Source: WBCSD Report of debate on

VARIOUS INTEREST GROUPS IN CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

1. Responsibility towards Consumers
2. Responsibility towards Employees
3. Responsibility towards Shareholders
4. Responsibility towards Government
5. Responsibility towards Community
6. Responsibility towards Suppliers

EMERGING ISSUES IN THE FIELD OF CSR

Human Rights- Women’s rights, indigenous people survival rights, rights for differently able, freedom of speech.

Employee Rights- Freedom of association and the right to collective bargaining, elimination of forced labour, abolition of all child labour, and the overcome of discrimination in occupation and employment.

Environmental Protection- improvements in business eco-efficiency protect the physical environment through their eco- friendly practices.

Community Involvement- Running Community assistance programs, supporting educational, health and safety needs, sponsoring and motivating employees to work voluntarily in the community.

Supplier Relations- The ‘two-way street’ relation is needed by both the parties and a fair trade practices is to be there.

Monitoring- Measuring and reporting of the performance of the business.

Stakeholder Rights- Not only including shareholders there is also concern about customers, employees, communities, suppliers and government also.

OBJECTIVE

1. To study various CSR practices done by leading organizations in Rural Development.
2. To examine sector wise CSR initiatives take by corporate houses to provide basic services to the rural community for development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research focus on the 'impact of CSR on rural growth and development' and analyzing various areas of corporate initiatives for the sustainable rural development. The Paper is developed on the basis of secondary data, which is collected from varied sources like corporate CSR policy book and their website, Journals, Magazines, Periodicals, Newspapers and Books to answer the research question

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Social responsibility of business, popularly known Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has gain importance at world level and this corporate concept was originated and developed in some countries like USA, UK, Canada, France, Germany and these countries motivated companies to put their involvement in social welfare programs. Brown (1953) explained CSR as, "obligation (of manager) to pursue those policies, to make those lives of action which are desirable in terms of objectives and values of our society". WBCSD (2000) defines CSR as "the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well as of the local community and society at large." Geoffrey (2001) examined the growth of the CSR concept & its four important components: Legal, economic, ethical & altruistic duties. It also highlighted various perspectives on role of business for society, from money making to providing welfare service to the community. He accounted that most of the controversy and confusion over CSR is due to lack of distinction between ethical, strategic and altruistic forms of CSR. Scott (2007) reviewed five themes inculcated in the definitions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) that responsibility towards society and community, promoting citizenship and democracy, reducing income inequalities prevailing in the country and reducing poverty, employee rights and ethical behavior, improving working conditions. Fred (2008) explained the question. Is corporate social responsibility (CSR) a business duty? As many grapple with, or just a gentle delusion? Jones (1980) granted that business managers actually have a responsibility to make groups apart from shareholders and managers are focused with five questions: Firstly, Who are these groups, Secondly, what number of these groups are to be served, Thirdly, what are their interests that are very important, Fourthly, how their interests can be equalized, and Fifthly, what amount of business money are to be invested to fulfill these interest? Ritson M. and Elliott, R, (1999) Since CSR is the path in which corporate tries to affect the society in a flourished way and the general public is also affected by advertisement made by corporate. Amalric et al. (2005) commented that there are two sources of benefits from CSR activities of the corporate. The first source is from stakeholders of the business for sound corporate conduct and second driver behind the adoption of CSR activities by companies is the government binding regulations. Ken Coghill et al. (2005) accounted CSR in their report submitted to the inquiry on the same in Australian Parliamentary that there are three forces of CSR in existence: Firstly, a *Business Strategy*

formulated to forecast the threats and risks to the company's shareholders interest. Secondly, *Ethical and Moral Values* i.e. CSR as a policy should be based upon the same that act as a benefit to the company as well as social interest. Thirdly, *Social Sustainability* i.e. CSR is a way to achieve the sustainability for society as well as environment. Apart from these three forces, all the three authors argued that first force i.e. strategic approach is the dominant among all as generally companies are ready to face the political, economic and technological challenges in future but to manage the modern challenge related to social and environmental issues they have to make CSR strategies that further proceed to CSR corporate governance. Campbell (2007) in its test that is related to sort the factors governing organization to move towards CSR and he examined that financial condition of the company, economic viability and state regulations are main factors to it.

CORPORATE INITIATIVES TOWARDS HOLISTIC RURAL DEVELOPMENT

There are numerous ways the corporate serve the society. They account for financial aid to providing services of basic nature. Few areas of rural scenario are discussed below where various initiatives are taken to develop them.

LIVELIHOOD

GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) a British Pharmaceutical Company initiated a Sustainable livelihood program through a Livelihood Training Centers named *Yuva Parivartan* in Peth Taluka of Nasik in Maharashtra to impart skill training such as in the field of computer, tailoring, nursing, beauty, agricultural etc. to make youths more employable and reduce the labour migration. Approximately more than 2500 youths are trained so far and most of them are currently employed.

TATA a giant India based Multinational Corporation has so far ran numerous social welfare programs in the rural as well as urban areas like a group company **Tata Consultancy Services** (TCS) started a program *Maitree* which focus on imparting training and skill development to the visually impaired. They established an *Advanced Computer Training Centre* (ACTC) where these differently able sections are taught practical application of learned skill and knowledge in the corporate field.

Apart from this, **Tata Motors** also initiated vocational training program through cooperative societies to the women and youth in computers and farm development, special program for women with the help of *self-help group* (SHGs) concept in vocational trades like tailoring, weaving, beautician and technical training such as motor mechanics and electricians etc.

Tata Chemicals Society for Rural Development (TCSRSD) aid in generating livelihood for women of rural areas through a handicraft development project started in 2002 in Okhamandal village of Gujarat with a group of 25 rural women that is now grown as empowering brand as *Okhai*. This is promoted through SHGs and women are trained with various business techniques like teamwork, marketing, quality, production, redesigning of Okhai products and costing etc. Currently 14 villages and more than 450 women have accounted benefit from it.

Citi India, for the economic growth and development of those remote hill rural areas of Uttarakhand where agriculture activities are very peculiar, has collaborated with a NGO Appropriate Technology India (AT India) that actually works for mountain communities to start a Sustainable Livelihoods for Rural Producers Program that is empowering peoples specially women in various other rural produce such as sericulture, horticulture and cultivation of organic species and augment them to make sustain their micro enterprise.

HEALTH

Hemophiliacs Education and Transformation (HEAT) project started by **ONGC** in collaboration with Hemophilia Federation India (HFI) to take curative action for the Children with Hemophilia (CwH) through educating them. The HFI will identify country wise 1000 CwH that are in age group of 5 to 18 years and are below poverty line and fund will be provided by ONGC to run the project.

Infosys has made a foundation and constructed Hospitals and Rest Rooms (*Dharamshalas*) at various hospitals in country such as built a Infosys Super- Specialty hospital at Sassoon Hospital in Pune, constructed a *Dharmashala* at Kidwai Memorial Institute of Oncology in Bangalore, Built a hospital for tribes at H.D. Kote, in the southern Indian state of Karnataka, Donated high-tech surgical equipment to hospitals in Mysore, Bijapur, Bellary and Hubli in Karnataka, Donated money to SPARSHA toward conducting screening camp for knee-related issues among retired school teachers and many more initiatives are taken by Infosys in the field of Health.

GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) with a NGO Institute for Indian Mother & Child (IIMC) committed towards good maternal and child health in rural areas of West Bengal by educating mothers and providing various primary medical facilities to pre, neo and postnatal care for mother and her child to avoid various deformities in delivery like premature babies etc. It also provides supplementary nutritional mixed diet to all pregnant or weaning mothers along with newborn baby to care against malnutrition diseases of children. It has ultimately help in reduction of maternal mortality rate (MMR) by training Traditional Birth Attendant (TBA) for safe child birth. IIMC till now covered 950 villages to cater 300 mothers and 26000 children. GSK has also initiated a *Tribal Welfare Projects* in Peth Taluka, Nashik, Maharashtra through its Rural Health Development Organization and charitable trust Gramin Aarogya Vikas Sanstha (GAVS) for their upliftment. It provides support for education, health, transport, malnutrition etc.

Tata Medical Center (TMC) a renowned Cancer institution of country at Kolkata offering care and medical service to the cancer patients and their kin where as in west Tata Memorial Hospital (TMH) Mumbai, practicing a huge Cancer patients. Patients from north, east and also from Bangladesh came to TMC and here 50% of beds are reserved for those who are unable to bear the cost and other 50% beds are subsidized. Other charges are covered by charitable funding.

Tata Steel Rural Development Society (TSRDS) a society of Tata Steel works on three principles Emphasizing Prevention, Curative Services and Promotion to awareness about health and hygiene. Various clinics are opened in Jharkhand and Jamshedpur which tries to cater Tuberculosis, Contraception and HIV-AIDS. As per its principle TSRDS is not giving everything

free but make a village health fund and every visitor of clinic pays a sum of Rs. 2 in to a box. So far Rs. 290,000 has been collected; this amount of money is used back for the community. In continuation *Tata Chemicals Magadi's* effort to provide healthcare particularly on HIV/AIDS.

EDUCATION

Infosys Foundation promotes primary education in underprivileged children with global partnership through establishing libraries and other infrastructural facilities. It founded more than 50,000 libraries in rural schools in Karnataka where more than 50,000 sets of books were given to rural schools of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Odhisha and Kerala costing 8000 to 10,000 per set apart from this it also setup more than 10,150 libraries in rural government schools also. Infosys foundation is having collaboration with *Center for Environment Education (CEE)*, Bangalore, to give orientation to the teachers of science and environment. It also provides scholarship to the meritorious PhD students at Gulbarga University, Karnataka.

Forbes Marshall supports fun preschools launched in 1999, named as *Gammatwadis* which prepares young children for formal schooling. They also partnered with the local municipal authorities to expand the service training programs for more than a hundred Balwadi teachers. They also joined with an NGO named *Akanksha* which involved in teaching and supporting children by giving them a strong educational foundation, self esteem and values, and help them plan a steady livelihood as a step towards improving their standard of living. They also contributed to create motivational centers called *Prerna Kendras* for children from municipal schools and activity centers or study hall facilities called *Balbhavans* at their Welfare Centre and support to the 'School Library Project' are some of the other programs they are involved with to ignite young minds, build self esteem and inculcate values for a socially responsible community.

Tata Consultancy Services take initiatives to improve adult literacy condition. Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) came up with a *Computer Based Functional Literacy (CBFL) programme* in Beeramguda village in Medak district of Andhra Pradesh. CBFL is a e-learning system to help illiterates adult to speak the language and learn the skills of reading, writing and arithmetic. TCS core competency in software development to develop CBFL software for *National Literacy Mission (NLM)* for conducting research. The CBFL method uses the combination of graphic patterns and audio patterns leads to recognition, retention and recall of words. Primers developed by the NLM often supplement the programme.

The Indian Oil Scholarships Scheme as part of Indian Oil's social responsibility programme includes the attractive scholarships for the bright students selected on 'merit-cum-means' basis. The organization provides 2600 scholarships covering the *first year students of 10+ / ITI, Engineering, MBBS and MBA*. The scheme also provides special encouragement for girl students, physically challenged students, students from Jammu & Kashmir and North-eastern States of India. Indian Oil Sports to encourage young players also awards scholarships to motivate new talent and to create a pool of sportspersons from which they later select sport appointees for the Corporation.

AGRICULTURE

Tata Hitachi Construction Machinery (THCM) conducts various agricultural based training programmes in the villages to enhance their efficiency and productivity as well as income. THCM helps the villagers to start cultivation on their barren land and for creating water harvesting structures to store rain water to increase water availability for house hold and other activities like pisciculture, duck farming, vegetable farming etc. Under THCM's *lift irrigation project* in the Hurling village, they provided pipes and cable connection, which has enabled the villagers to bring 30 acres of land under multiple cropping as well as they provides good variety of high yielding hybrid seeds to farmers for vegetable cultivation.

Zuari Agro Chemicals Limited demonstrated Low cost Drip Irrigation System at Succor, Bardez Goa. The cost of installing Drip system can be recovered in just two crop rotations. Zuari Agro Chemicals Limited also explained about the special fertilisers which is favorable for cultivation with drip irrigation. *Zuari has collaborated with Department of Agriculture and Karnataka Govt. and Pesticide Manufacturers Association* to educating farmers on safer use of pesticides and how pesticides should be handled safely so that it could not harm to human and environment. They organizes campaign on 11th November in which 15 farmers were organized for meetings in different parts of Yadgir, Gulbarga, Raichur, Bidar, Bagalkot and Bijapur districts where farmers highlighted important points during these meetings related to Safety Measures in handling pesticides, precautions to be taken before purchase, advantages of sourcing products from authorized dealers.

ITC's Livestock and Animal Husbandry Programme focus rural communities which is primarily based on the aim to strengthen and improving rural livelihood through both farm and non-farm activities. The programme including genetic improvements of cattle through artificial insemination to produce high-yielding crossbreed progenies and upgrade to high-yield livestock and form co-operatives to market their milk as well as ITC trains and equips technicians to provide an integrated package consisting of artificial insemination, cattle health and nutrition, pregnancy and post-natal services right at the farmer's doorstep. They established over 256 *Cattle Development Centers (CDCs)* covering more than 10,500 villages for providing artificial inseminations, vaccination and nutrition services.

PepsiCo's Contract Farming Model provides assistance to farmers. According to contract farming concept the company transfers agricultural best practices and technology and procures the produce at a pre-agreed price. To support the initiative company conduct farm trials of new varieties of potato, chilli, corn, peanut and other crops on 27-acre research and demonstration farm set up in Punjab as well as their India's technical team launched a high quality seed programme to avail early generation and disease-free seeds to farmers. Moreover, PepsiCo India has partnered with more than 11,000 farmers across various states like Punjab, U.P., Karnataka, Bihar, Gujarat and Maharashtra for the supply of world class chip-grade potatoes. With the State Bank of India, PepsiCo partnered to assist contract farmers to get soft loans to reduce their cost of cultivation. In Rajasthan, PepsiCo India has also partnered with 1,200 farmers and tie-up with the United Breweries Group for barley cultivation.

Vedanta's Project Jaibik, Organic Cotton Cultivation was initiated to facilitate farmers to grow cotton organically which entailed using cultural practices, bio fertilizers and biological

pest controls rather than inorganic fertilizers and pesticide. VAL has supporting to improve the existing skill, planning and creating appropriate linkages both backward and forward as well as they provide training to farmers for making and using organic manure which shows sustained as well as enhanced soil productivity. Total 178.96 acres of land cultivated by 92 farmers in 8 villages of Lanjigarh Block and have been insured against natural calamities. Vedanta's CSR department for *cash crop farming* identifies various groups of farmers from different villages through a survey to give them a series of Training Sessions & Workshops to use modern and best agricultural techniques with quality seeds, organic manure and other support provided by VAL.

ENVIRONMENT

PepsiCo India taken initiatives to strengthen its *Solid Waste Management* with an environmental NGO named as Exnora. This partnership provides a clean environment to more than 450000 people across Pammal, Chennai, Nagapattinam, Tenkasi and Cuddalore in Tamil Nadu, Sangareddy in Andhra Pradesh and Panipat, Haryana. They are educating people that how to recycle waste, how waste is converted into high quality organic manure through vermi-culture, how waste such as PET and plastics, waste paper and tetra packs are recycled. They also involved in community awareness programmes.

Zensar Technology's Green agenda is an initiative dedicated to become an environment friendly organization and to running an Energy Efficient business for its associates, customers, community and stakeholders. The Company, under its Green Agenda, extended its Green activities to supporting environment friendly activities by reducing wastes, emissions, recycling as well as creating awareness about their environmental responsibilities through campaigns. Moreover, Zensar tie-up with the NGO called *Association for Learning, Education and Training* (ALERT) works for the green movement which has also in a partnership with the Pune Municipal Corporation (PMC) with a aim to develop 2 acre of land mass into a biodiversity park for over 35 different species of flora and fauna near Zensar's Kharadi Campus in Pune.

Tata Housing Development Company's environment-friendly approaches committed to "maintain a high standard of protection for our employees, the environment, natural resources, equipment and the public" in the conduct of its business. Moreover, they made commitment to develop sustainable ways of building and construction. Tata Housing one among construction companies which following 'green' standards for its projects. The company glued to norms stipulated by the *Indian Green Building Council* (IGBC), *Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design* (LEED) and *Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment*.

Taj Safaris limited is making its contribution for preserving India's incredible natural treasures. They provide their customers with the amazing wildlife experience by following *sustainable eco-tourism model* for which Taj Safar has taken various initiatives including the example of Pashan Garh Lodge which created a water recycling system to recycle grey water from the staff village for use in the vegetable garden which have transformed the staff village area into a flourishing vegetable garden as well as they create a garbage incinerator, which provides ash that is combined with the compost to produce organic fertilisers for the vegetable garden. Another example include *Improvised Smokeless Chulha* by Taj Safaris newly introduced in local communities having two burners, which can be used to cook two items at the same time

reduces consumption of fuel wood by 40 to 45 percent with reduced cooking time and healthier living conditions.

COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

ONGC movement 'PURA' (Providing Urban Amenities to Rural Areas) initiated to avail urban amenities to rural areas which provide gas-based power from isolated & idle gas wells in each state where ONGC produces Oil & Gas and availability of isolated gas like Tripura, Assam, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat. In this project ONGC partnered with NABARD for Soft loan & entrepreneurial development, TERI for Project study & development, Wartsila for power generation, Thermax for cold chain.

Tata Tea's Power of 49 campaign aims to empower and educate India's women voters. The initiative highlighted that women form approximately 49 percent of the electoral base. The mission is to create 100 million informed voters as well as by using every platform to aware and connect large numbers of women voters. Tata's another initiative is Tata Tea's extremely successful *Jaago Re campaign*; launch in 2007 has initiated social change by awaring with actual human rights and duties as a citizen of India.

Infosys Rural Development goal is an initiative taken for the well-being of people living in rural areas to ensure sustainable development for which the *Infosys Foundation* working with local administration for constructing roads, providing drainage systems and electricity, and rehabilitate facilities for victims from tsunami, earthquake, cyclone, drought -affected areas. The Foundation has donated more than INR 40 crore to the projects such as awareness campaigns on hygiene, sanitation, vocational training and entrepreneurship. Moreover, they also support the midday meal program of the *Akshaya Patra Foundation*, Bangalore, for poor children in North Karnataka. They also made their contribution with the Red Cross Society to supply aid equipment to improve the physically challenged, leprosy and hunger conditions, constructed hostel buildings for poor students, orphanages in rural areas, built girls hostels, donate a hall for people with physical disabilities in Karnataka, gives training to tribal communities in agriculture, horticulture, sericulture, floriculture, apiculture, fishing, dairy, poultry, welding, and carpentry of Karnataka and Orissa, donated sewing machines to women in rural areas of Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka, provide training in hygiene and sanitation, health and nutrition, and skills and livelihood and initiated the construction of 10,000 toilets in the backward districts.

ITC's Women's empowerment programme is a commitment towards social goals and its initiative is to build the communities and households around ITC's units. The programme include the challenging task of creating sustainable livelihoods for communities, and approximately they covered over 20,780 women through 1736 self-help groups and over 38,000 women have been gainfully employed either through micro-enterprises, or were assisted with loans to pursue income generating activities. *ITC's Women's Empowerment programme* is yet another successful model that shows ITC's long-standing allegiance to Triple Bottom Line Objectives which is closely interlinked with ITC's *Agarbatti* business, and today this activity provides supplementary incomes to more than 4000 women.

CONCLUSION

Thus, from the study it can be concluded that the business houses in India can play a major role in the process of rural development by grooming basic areas of rural services and sectors like employment, health, agriculture, education, environment and community development etc. As far as developmental activities arise at the door step of the rural people, the rate of rural migration will slide down. The CSR programs that corporate houses run are actually joint effort of government, various NGOs and corporate in social- making context. According to ministry of corporate affairs (MCA) notification in Sec. 135 and Schedule VII of the Companies Act, 2013, that is related to CSR. The norms will apply to the companies with at least Rs. 5 crore net profit or Rs. 1,000 crore turnover or Rs. 500 crore net worth as these companies will have to spend 2% of their net profit or three-year average annual net profit on CSR activities. Hence, Corporate houses need to run more and more CSR programme which empower rural India and led it in mainstream.

REFERENCES

1. AMALRIC, FRANCK & JASON HAUSER (2005) 'Economic Drivers of Corporate Responsibility Activities'. *Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 20, p.27-38.
2. BROWN HOWARD R, (1953) *Social Responsibility of Business*, Harper & Brother, New York
3. CAMPBELL, J. L. (2007) Why would corporations behave in socially responsible ways? An institutional theory of corporate social responsibility. *Academy of Management Review*, 32, p.946-967.
4. COGHILL, KEN, LEEORA BLACK & DOUG HOLMES (2005) Submission to the Australian Government, Parliamentary Joint Committee on Corporations and Financial Services: Inquiry into Corporate Social Responsibility. Available from: http://www.aph.gov.au/~media/wopapub/senate/committee/corporations_ctte/completed_inquiries/2004_07/corporate_responsibility/submissions/sub71_pdf.ashx [Accessed on 28th Dec. 2014]
5. ENS Economic Bureau (2014) Mandatory 2% CSR spend set to kick in from April 1. Indian Express, [Online], 28th February. Available from: <http://indianexpress.com/article/business/economy/mandatory-2-csr-spend-set-to-kick-in-from-april-1/#sthash.MNWCVCrf.dpuf> [Accessed: 04 Jan 2015].
6. JONES, T. M. (1980). Corporate social responsibility, revisited, redefined. *California Management Review*, 22(3).p.59-67.
7. P. Lantos Geoffrey. (2001) The boundaries of strategic corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*. 18(7) p. 595 –632.
8. ROBINS, FRED. (2008) Why corporate social Responsibility should be popularized but not imposed, *Corporate Governance*. 8(3)p. 330 –341.
9. RITSON, M. AND ELLIOTT, R. (1999). The social uses of advertising: An ethnographic study of adolescent advertising audiences. *Journal of Consumer Research*. 26(3) p. 260-277.
10. SCOTT SIMEON (2007) Corporate Social Responsibility and the Fetter of Profitability. *Social Responsibility Journal*. 3(4). P. 31 – 39.
11. The World Business Council on Sustainable Development. (2000). *Corporate Social Responsibility: Meeting Change Expectation*, p.3-11. [Online] Available from:

- <http://www.wbcds.org/Pages/Adm/Download.aspx?ID=108&ObjectTypeId=7> [Accessed: 10 Jan 2015]
12. GSK Ltd [Online] Available from: <http://www.gsk-india.com/corporate-ruralprojects.html> [Accessed: 02 Jan 2015]
 13. TATA. Available from: http://www.tata.co.in/sustainability/sub_index/Company-initiatives [Accessed: 02 Jan 2015]
 14. Zuari. Available from: <http://zuari.in/socialresponsibility> [Accessed: 02 Jan 2015]
 15. Zensar Technology. Available from: <http://csrworld.net/csr-activities-of-zensar-technologies.asp> [Accessed: 04 Jan 2015]
 16. Vedanta. Available from: <http://www.vedantaaluminium.com/csr-updates.htm> [Accessed: 04 Jan 2015]
 17. TATA. Available from: <http://www.tata.co.in/search/label/Education> [Accessed: 04 Jan 2015]
 18. Forbes Marshall Available from: http://www.forbesmarshall.com/fm_micro/csr/CSRPageDetails.aspx?pagename=Education [Accessed: 05 Jan 2015]
 19. Tata, Available from: <http://www.tata.co.in/search/label/Health> [Accessed: 05 Jan 2015]
 20. Tata. Available from: <http://www.tata.co.in/search/label/Environment> [Accessed: 05 Jan 2015]
 21. Tata. Available from: http://www.tata.co.in/search/label/Community_initiatives [Accessed: 05 Jan 2015]
 22. Citi India, Available from: <http://csrworld.net/Sustainable-Livelihoods-for-Rural-Producers-Program-CSR-initiative-of-citi-india.asp> [Accessed: 07 Jan 2015]
 23. Tata. Available from: <http://www.tata.co.in/search/label/Employability> [Accessed: 07 Jan 2015]
 24. Tata. Available from: <http://www.tata.co.in/search/label/Entrepreneurship> [Accessed: 07 Jan 2015]
 25. Infosys. Available from: <http://www.infosys.com/infosys-foundation/initiatives/rural-development.asp> [Accessed: 07 Jan 2015]
 26. ICT. Available from: <http://www.itcportal.com/sustainability/investing-in-social-development.aspx> [Accessed: 03 Jan 2015]
 27. IOCL. Available from: <http://csrworld.net/csr-activities-of-indian-oil-corporation-limited.asp> [Accessed: 03 Jan 2015]
 28. ONGC. Available from: <http://csrworld.net/ongc-corporate-social-responsibility.asp> [Accessed: 03 Jan 2015]